

Scaling up CEI pilots:
Discover the open calls of O-
CEI and COP-PILOT

Welcome and introduction

Maria Giuffrida, Trust-IT

The event will be recorded and will be made available on the CEI-Sphere, O-CEI and COP-PILOT websites afterwards

We do encourage you to enter any question in the dedicated Q/A box placed in the lower toolbar.

You can follow the chat to be informed and receive links on the main references mentioned during the session.

1. Establish a solid ground for inter-LSP cooperation ...**analysing use cases and their deployment environments to create “Spheres”** that increase **visibility of what is being done and by whom**, facilitate interoperability and accelerate results-driven collaboration.
2. Develop an extensive, **data-driven understanding of European CEI market** focusing on the most strategic sectors for Europe and with a customised focus on use-cases and LSPs.
3. Support a **privacy-preserving open edge ecosystem** (incl. Startups, corporates and system integrators)....aligned with the European Data Strategy, the Chips JU and other national and regional initiatives.
4. Build a Sphere specific **CEI technology backbone kit** that supports the open edge ecosystem and market scalability of LSPs solutions ...that incorporate guidance on **standards, interoperability, open-source orchestration, and architectures**.
5. Curate an **extensive CEI stakeholder ecosystem drawing expertise from** other existing communities (Standards, IPCEI, ChipsJU, EPoSS, INSIDE, Open Europe Forum etc.) to create awareness and generate impact.

Overview

Coordinator

Partners

7

Type

CSA

Coordinator

Partners

58

Pilots

8 | 27 scenarios

FR, IT, ES, IE, HR, RO, AT, MT, CY, CH

Coordinator

Partners

45

Pilots

4 clusters | 12 use cases

DE, ES, SE, IE, FI, GR, CH

- 11:00 - Welcome and introduction, Maria Giuffrida Trust-IT
- 11:05 – O-CEI First Open Call: Outcomes and Lessons Learned, Ignacio Lacalle Úbeda, Universitat Politècnica de València
- 11:25 COP-PILOT First Open Call: Scope, Requirements and Timeline, Rafael Rodrigues, Digital4Planet
- 11:45 Panel discussion with Ioanna Drigkopoulou, Netcompany-Intrasoft, Joanna Makocka, F6S and Ignacio Lacalle Úbeda, Universitat Politècnica de València
- 12:15 Q&A
- 12:30 Conclusion

The graphic features logos for Coppilot, CEI-Sphere (part of EU CloudEdgeIoT.eu), and O-CEI. The main text reads: "Scaling up CEI pilots: Discover the open calls of O-CEI and COP-PILOT". A "SAVE THE DATE" box indicates the event is on "12 Feb 2026" from "11am-12:30pm CET". A vertical "WEBINAR" label is on the left, and a "Funded by the European Union" logo is at the bottom left. The background includes illustrations of servers, a globe, and a smartphone.

copppilot **CEI-Sphere** part of EU CloudEdgeIoT.eu **O-CEI**

Scaling up CEI pilots:
**Discover the open calls
of O-CEI and COP-PILOT**

WEBINAR **SAVE THE DATE**
12 Feb 2026
11am-12:30pm CET

Funded by the European Union

O-CEI First Open Call: Outcomes and Lessons Learned from the OC

O-CEI: Open Cloud-Edge-IoT Platform Uptake in Large Scale Cross-Domain Pilots

Dr. Ignacio Lacalle

Universitat Politècnica de València

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- Call and Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2024-DATA-01-03 Piloting emerging Smart IoT Platforms and decentralized intelligence
- Type of project: IA
- Total budget: 31,347,300 € - EU Granted amount: 23,140,063.63 €
- Grant Agreement N°: 101189589
- Duration: **1st Jan 2025**– June 2028 (42 months)
- Project Coordinator: Carlos E. Palau Salvador (UPV)
- Field of action: Energy efficiency, energy flexibility, edge computing, resources orchestration, demand/production, collaboration, cross-domain, marketplaces, virtualization, data sovereignty
- N° partners: 60 (incl. three 3LPs)
 - *From 19 countries*: Spain, Greece, Switzerland, France, Malta, Romania, Germany, Austria, Italy, Poland, Cyprus, Ireland, Sweden, Denmark, Slovenia, Portugal, Finland, Belgium and Croatia.
- **Cascade funding: 4.000.000€ structured in two rounds**
- Work Packages: Project Coordination, Formalization of pilots and Open Platform requirements, O-CEI Open Platform and blueprints development, Execution of O-CEI Large Scale Pilots, Evaluation and Assessment, and Market uptaking, results exploitation and transferability.

O-CEI Open Calls Global Overview

- **1st Open call** for **Upscaling projects** to select up to **24 service/technology providers (single, SMEs)** testing the components and **developing edge solutions** (executable apps and services) that will extend the functionalities of **–adding value to- the 8 pilots** developed within the consortium.
- **2nd Open call** for **Uptake projects** to select up to **8 use cases extending the deployment of O-CEI** open platform as blueprints, either in **additional use cases** within the 6 sectors (energy, automotive, logistics, telecommunications, urban and agrifood areas) or proposing pilots into new domains.

Select up to 32 third-party projects (TP) through 2 Open Calls:		
Call type	UPSCALING projects	UPTAKE projects
Objective / Scope	Select Service/ Technology Providers testing the components and developing edge solutions of the 8 pilots developed within the consortium.	Select use cases extending the use of the open platform.
no. of Third-Party Projects	24 (initially 26)	8 (initially 7)
Type of beneficiary	Individual SMEs (including start-ups) from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU Member State and its Overseas Countries and Territories (OCT) - Horizon Europe Associated Countries 	Consortia of a tech/service provider and end-user from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU Member State and its Overseas Countries and Territories (OCT) - Horizon Europe Associated Countries Consortia have to be composed of a maximum of 2 entities and need to include at least one SME/Startup.
Financial support	EUR 100,000	EUR 200,000
Support Program duration	7 months (initially 8) -> no change in Amendment	11 months

WP / Task	Start date	End date
OC1	T1.4 Open Call preparatory tasks	01 Apr 2025 - 31 Aug 2025
	T1.4 OC launch, dissemination & management	01 Sep 2025 - 03 Nov 2025
	T1.4 Evaluation & Selection of proposals	04 Nov 2025 - 31 Dec 2025
	T1.4 SGA signature	01 Jan 2026 - 28 Feb 2026
T6.4 FSTP Management	01 Mar 2026 - 30 Sep 2026	
OC2	T1.4 Open Call preparatory tasks	01 Jul 2026 - 30 Sep 2026
	T1.4 OC launch, dissemination & management	01 Oct 2026 - 30 Nov 2026
	T1.4 Evaluation & Selection of proposals	01 Dec 2026 - 31 Jan 2027
	T1.4 SGA signature	01 Feb 2027 - 31 Mar 2027
T6.4 FSTP Management	01 Apr 2027 - 01 Feb 2028	

1st period of activity: **March-September 2026**

2nd period of activity: **April 2027-February 2028**

O-CEI 1st Open Call – Work performed (1)

PREPARATION OF MATERIAL

SUBMISSION DEADLINE
20 November 2025, 17:00 CET.

APPLICATION AND OWN SITE

DISCORD CHANNEL TO SOLVE QUESTIONS

2 WEBINARS

SESSION IN AIOTI 2025

O-CEI Horizon 1st Open Call - 1st Explanatory Webinar, September 22nd, 2025
196 visualizaciones • hace 4 meses

O-CEI Horizon 1st Open Call - 2nd Explanatory Webinar, October 17th, 2025
118 visualizaciones • hace 3 meses

<https://opportunities.getonepass.eu/applications/686b9c817bcf244135cad203/start>

O-CEI: Open CloudEdgeIoT Platform Uptake in Large Scale Cross-Domain Pilots 1st Open Call

- **Funding available:** amount of EUR 100,000 per FSTP beneficiary
- **Support available:** a 7 month programme
- **Application deadline:** 20th of November, 2025, 17:00 Brussels Time
- **Eligible applicants:** Individual SMEs, (including StartUps) located in EU Member States

Open Call Package of Documents:

- **Guide for Applicants** - The Guide for Applicants is step-by-step guide that contains all the information you need to know to apply.
- **Technical Guidelines** - The list of O-CEI challenges with description.
- **Pilot 1 Description**
- **Pilot 2 Description**
- **Pilot 3 Description**
- **Pilot 4 Description**
- **Pilot 5 Description**
- **Pilot 6 Description**
- **Pilot 7 Description**
- **Pilot 8 Description**

• **Collaboration Agreement Template** - The SubGrant Agreement that will be signed by the beneficiary and the granting authority.

• **Privacy Note** - Information clause for personal data processing in the O-CEI 1st Open Call

O-CEI will launch 2 different Open Calls:

- **1st Open call for Upscaling projects to select up to 24 service/technology providers**
- **2nd Open call for Uptake projects to select up to 8 use cases extending the deployment of existing pilots into new domains.**

O-CEI DISCORD COMMUNITY

HOW TO JOIN THE O-CEI DISCORD COMMUNITY

- Scan the QR code or use the invitation link.
- Log in or create your account.
- Select "O-CEI" from the list of European projects during the onboarding in: "Are you interested in any of these European Projects?".

You will find the O-CEI community inside the "Connected World" category.

Engage directly with our team to get real-time support and exchange knowledge with fellow professionals. Stay informed about project updates, and the latest advancements in cloud-edge innovation.

Join O-CEI Helpdesk on DISCORD - Quick Guide

1. Scan the QR code or use the invitation link from eu.DEEPTECH (Power by FundingBox).
2. Create your account
On the platform, log in or sign up with your email and confirm your account via the email link.
3. Join the O-CEI network
In the "What are you interested in?" section, choose O-CEI from the list of projects. If it's not listed, go to the "eu.DEEPTECH Connected World" section, and click on "select-your-project". Then, click the bulb icon to complete the process and join the O-CEI community.

JOIN Discord

O-CEI 1st Open Call – Work performed (2)

O-CEI 1st Open Call - SUBMITTED

249 PROPOSALS
SUBMITTED

37 COUNTRIES

Greece	37
Italy	30
Spain	25
Türkiye	20
France	12
Germany	10
Romania	10
Bulgaria	9
Slovenia	8
Estonia	6
Finland	6
Netherlands	6
Portugal	6
Austria	5
North Macedonia	5
Slovakia	5
United Kingdom	5
Croatia	5
Cyprus	4
Poland	4
Serbia	4
Belgium	3
Lithuania	3
Ukraine	3
Ireland	2
Israel	2
Latvia	2
Montenegro	2
Tunisia	2
Albania	1
Armenia	1
Bosnia and Herzegovina	1
Canada	1
Czechia	1
Malta	1
Norway	1
Sweden	1

O-CEI 1st Open Call - SELECTED BENEFICIARIES

**24 PROPOSALS
PRE-SELECTED**

13 COUNTRIES

Spain	6
Greece	5
France	2
Germany	2
Bulgaria	1
Croatia	1
Estonia	1
Ireland	1
Italy	1
Netherlands	1
Norway	1
Serbia	1

O-CEI 1st Open Call

PRE-SELECTED BENEFICIARIES

PILOT 1 - 7

PILOT 2 - 3

PILOT 3 - 3

PILOT 4 - 2

PILOT 5 - 3

PILOT 6 - 1

PILOT 7 - 2

PILOT 8 - 3

1st Open Call lessons learnt

- More applications than expected.
- Extensive communication (webinars, Discord).
- Committee – advisory role/member
- Good financial structure / explanation.
- Requirements to be added in the Open Call Package of Documents:
 - Date of creating the entity
 - Travel for the Support Programme Kick-off Meeting
 - Dates of each stage of evaluation

Tips for O-CEI's 2nd Open Call and for COP-PILOT

- Careful with separation of competences
- Engage pilot / cluster owners early in the process.
- Keep them engaged in all stages – communicating with enough advance.
- Enlarge the “reserve” pool of evaluators.
- **Be very accurate and transparent in all detailed inner processes:**
 - Funding priorities.
 - Tie breakups.
 - Who decides what and when.
 - Criteria per section

THANKS

FOR YOUR ATTENTION

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Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
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COP-PILOT OPEN CALL #1

CEI-Sphere OC Promotion
February 12, 2026 (Online)

Presenter
Rafael Oliveira Rodrigues (D4P)

Agenda

- Intro
- Scope
- Requirements
- Timeline
- Summary

Intro

COP-PILOT Project

Project Information

COP-PILOT
Grant agreement ID: 101189819

DOI
[10.3030/101189819](https://doi.org/10.3030/101189819)

EC signature date
9 December 2024

Start date **End date**
1 January 2025 31 December 2027

Funded under
Digital, Industry and Space

Total cost
€ 27 710 415,00

EU contribution
€ 22 499 384,25

Investment in EU policy priorities

- Digital agenda Clean air
- Artificial Intelligence Climate action
- Biodiversity

Coordinated by
NETCOMPANY S.A.
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COP-PILOT Open Calls

Open Call rounds	Duration of OC projects	Max funding (€)	Number of projects	Total funding (€)
COP-PILOT-OC1	8 months	200.000	8	1.600.00
COP-PILOT -OC2			12	2.400.00
Total			20	4.000.000

Scope

COP-PILOT Vision

COP-PILOT Architecture

Platform Components: Open + Standardized

COP-PILOT Comp.

 Secure Integration Fabric (SIF)

Open-Source Software

Related Standard and/or Open-source Community

RFC7519 on IWT
RFC5280: X.509
PKI

Platform Components: Open + Standardized

COP-PILOT Comp.

Related (open) Software/Technology

Lots of K8s variants are supported, such as microk8s, k3S, k9s, etc.

Any controller for managing private 5G resources (RAN, Transport, Core) can be integrated with OpenSlice, especially if it is described as a Kubernetes Custom Resource(CR)

Example 5G controller integrations already in place:

NOKIA's NAC OTE's Slice Manager ETSI OSM 5GC prov. (Open5GS)

COP-PILOT Cluster

Clusters are *groups of firms, related economic actors, and institutions* located near* each other and with sufficient scale to develop specialised expertise, services, resources, suppliers and skills

*Near may correspond to either business or geographic proximity

Definition

Cluster 1

Business Integration in Mining

Cluster 2

Valencia Smart City

Cluster 3A

AgriTech Transformation and Sustainability Initiative (ATSI)

Cluster 3E

Edge Intelligence for Energy Grid Reliability

Cluster 4

Smart Vineyards & Sustainable Winery Ecosystems

EU Cluster policy: [link](#)

Requirements

COP-PILOT: How to Apply?

Submission Steps:

1. Read the [Guides](#)
2. Complete the Proposal following the [proposal guide](#)
3. Prepare [PDFs](#) (Proposal, Declaration of Honour, SME Checklist)
4. Submit [online](#)

Timings:

1. Call Opens: 16-02-2026 9h CET
2. Deadline: 17-04-2026 17h CET
3. Evaluation: May 2026
4. Start: June 2026

Where?

- Select your favourite cluster

Cluster 1
Business
Integration
in Mining

Cluster 2
Valencia
Smart City

Cluster 3A
AgriTech
Transformation
and
Sustainability
Initiative (ATSI)

Cluster 3E
Edge Intelligence
for Energy Grid
Reliability

Cluster 4
Smart
Vineyards &
Sustainable
Winery
Ecosystems

- 1-2 projects per Cluster will be awarded

How?

Workflow 1: Service Providers

- **Target:** Applicants with software solution (AI, analytics, automation)
- **Goal:** Onboard your service using our LLM portal & deploy on testbeds
- **Benefit:** Automated SLA assurance & access to real industrial data

Workflow 2: Infrastructure Owners

- **Target:** Applicants with hardware (testbeds, labs, compute clusters)
- **Goal:** Connect private domain to ecosystem using "Auto-Pilot" feature
- **Benefit:** Monetize resources by exposing them "as-a-service" to federation

Managed Edge Node Operator for On-Prem Edge in Underground Mines

(UC 1.4 → UC1.1-1.3)

A service provider that can integrate, operate, and maintain on-prem edge compute nodes deployed across mining sites globally, under strict safety and security constraints

Core responsibilities:

- **Deploy & integrate** edge nodes into the mine's digital and security infrastructure (identity/access, network segmentation, hardening)
- **Operate & maintain** nodes with high operational robustness (monitoring, patching, updates, incident response), including in harsh environments
- **Coordinate with application providers** to ensure end-to-end functionality and edge-cloud connectivity when applicable, while supporting local survivability, data sovereignty and low latency

Example project for Cluster 2

- **City of Valencia:** *Municipal buildings management*
 - *SME/consortia for data analytics/decision to action*
- **UPV:**
 - *Smart Access and Resource Management at UPV Campus*
 - *SME/consortia for sensing + data analytics/decision to action*
 - *Robotic patrol and surveillance at UPV Campus (and/or Valencia City)*
 - *SME/consortia for robotics + security UCs*

Example project for Cluster 3A

Plant Sensor Prototypes

Develop novel leaf-mounted or in-soil sensors for nutrient, stress or pesticide detection, tested in parallel with existing wearables.

Smart Freshness Sensors for Packaged Produce

Develop and test sensors embedded in packaging to monitor spoilage indicators during distribution, feeding data to FMIS and traceability systems.

Onboard Tractor Activity Logging for FMIS Integration

Deploy tractor-mounted systems that automatically register cultivation activities and sync them with FMIS and blockchain for traceability and carbon accounting.

AR/XR Dashboard for Field Agronomists

Design an augmented/extended reality interface that visualizes FMIS alerts, crop stress areas and UGV missions in real-time during scouting.

Example project for Cluster 3E

Edge Intelligence for predictive Maintenance in RES

Expand cluster capabilities to integrate different types of RES (PV inverters, wind turbines etc.)

Flexibility modelling and harvesting techniques from residential feeders

Expand cluster capabilities to optimally harvest flexibility from new types of feeders

Industrial users (e.g., factories) offering surrogate or analytical models mapping flexibility potential to be exposed to DSOs.

Enrich the cluster through the integration of industrial users of different types

Edge AI analytics for EV Charging stations or Biomass plants or DSOs

Validation and comparison of different AI analytics at the edge for the pilots.

Example project for Cluster 4

Precision Agriculture – Vineyards:

- Multi-sensor monitoring, disease & yield prediction

Water & Production Efficiency:

- AI-driven irrigation, predictive maintenance, energy optimisation

Robotics & Automation:

- Autonomous vehicles, drones, 5G-enabled operations

Circular IoT:

- Sensor lifecycle management, reuse, e-waste reduction

Fullfill the Criteria

- **Project Overview**
- **Section 1 Excellence:**
 - **1.1 Detailed Description**
 - **1.2 Infrastructure Requirements**
- **Section 2 Impact:**
 - **2.1 Expected Impact and Sustainability**
 - **2.2 Expected Outcomes**
- **Section 3 Quality and efficiency of the implementation:**
 - **3.1 Work Plan & Timeline**
 - **3.2 Team Qualifications**
 - **3.3 Funding & Justification**

Criterion	Raw Score (0-5)	Weighting Factor	Max Possible Score	Minimum Weighted Threshold
1. Excellence	0-5	x 8	40 points	24 points
2. Impact	0-5	x 6	30 points	18 points
3. Implementation	0-5	x 6	30 points	18 points
TOTAL			100 POINTS	60 POINTS

Funding & Eligibility

Key Points:

- **Budget:** Total €1.6M available. Max **€200,000** per project (Lump Sum)
- **Funding Rate:** 100% of eligible costs
- **Eligibility:**
 - **SME-led:** Can be a single SME or a consortium (SME leader + partners like universities/large enterprises/RTO/NPO/Public institution)
 - **Location:** Must be in an EU Member State or Horizon Europe Associated Country
- **Duration:** 8 months execution + 2 months reporting (Starts ~June 2026)

Timeline

COP-PILOT OC Visual Timeline

Phase	Action Item	Start-End
Opening – Run OC1	Open Call announcement:	16-02-26
	Info webinar	March 2026
	Proposal submission	16-02-2026 9h CET 17-04-2026 17h CET

Open Calls Evaluation & Selection

Summary

Summary

- 1** Visit COP-PILOT Website ([link](#))
- 2** Read the available Documentation ([link](#))
- 3** Best of luck for your proposal!

THANKS FOR YOUR ATTENTION

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